

18. Uluslararası Dil, Edebiyat ve Kültür Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri
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ÖN SÖZ

18. Uluslararası Dil, Edebiyat ve Kültür Araştırmaları Kongresi, 08-11 Ekim 2024 tarihlerinde Ankara'da gerçekleşti. Bu kongre, Saybider Topluluğunun organizasyonunda ve başta Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli Üniversitesi, Mardin Artuklu Üniversitesi, Carthage University olmak üzere çeşitli yükseköğretim kurumlarının ilmi desteği ile düzenlenmektedir. Kongreye 6 farklı ülkeden davetli konuşmacı davet edilmiştir. Aynı zamanda Türkçe, İngilizce ve Arapça duyurular yapılarak bilim insanlarına çağrıda bulunulmuştur. Bu çağrılar sonrasında Türkiye hariç 13 farklı ülkeden (Birleşik Krallık, Cezayir, Çin, Endonezya, Fas, Filistin, Irak, İran, Mısır, Suriye, Suudi Arabistan Krallığı, Umman, Ürdün) sözlü bildiri kongre programına dâhil edilmiştir. Tüm bildiriler kör hakemlik sürecinden geçirildikten sonra sunuma kabul veya reddi gerçekleştirilmiştir. Bu süreç içerisinde bildirilerin önemli bir kısmına hakemlerden düzeltme talebi gelmiştir. Hakemler tarafından talep edilen düzeltmelerin yapılıp yapılmadığı da özenle kontrol edilmiş ve düzeltilerden sonra kabul mektupları düzenlenerek yazarlarına gönderilmiştir.

Başvuru süreci sonucunda 72'yi Türk bilim insanları tarafından ve 80'i farklı ülkelerden katılan bilim insanları tarafından hazırlanmış toplam 152 bildiri sözlü sunuma uygun bulunmuştur. Bu kitapta bilim insanlarının kongrede sunduğu bildirilerin tam metinlerine yer verilmiştir. Bu sunumların geniş kitlelere ulaşarak alana faydalı olmasını ve yeni çalışmalara ilham vermesini diliyorum.

Kongrenin bilim insanları arasındaki iletişimi kuvvetlendirmesini, bilgi alışverişini arttırmasını, ortak çalışma zeminlerini oluşturmasını, milletimize, insanlığa ve bilgiyle amel edenlere faydalı olmasını diliyorum.

Prof. Dr. Yakup Civelek
Düzenleme Kurulu Başkanı

مقدمة

يأتي هذا الكتاب نتيجًا لجهود مجموعة من الباحثين البارزين الذين شاركوا بأبحاثهم في المؤتمر الدولي الثامن عشر للغات والآداب والدراسات الثقافية، والذي عُقد في أنقرة خلال الفترة من 8 إلى 11 أكتوبر. يعد هذا المؤتمر أحد أبرز الفعاليات الأكاديمية التي تجمع بين مختلف التخصصات في مجال العلوم الإنسانية، حيث شارك فيه باحثون من أكثر من عشرين دولة من مختلف القارات، مما أضفى طابعًا عالميًا ومتنوعًا على المناقشات التي جرت.

تميز المؤتمر بالتنوع الثقافي واللغوي الذي انعكس في الأوراق البحثية المقدمة، حيث تناول الباحثون قضايا متعددة تشمل الأدب الكلاسيكي والمعاصر، اللغات الحديثة والقديمة، ودراسات الثقافة وتأثيراتها على المجتمعات المختلفة. ولم يقتصر النقاش على دراسة الأعمال الأدبية أو تحليل النصوص اللغوية فحسب، بل تطرق إلى استكشاف العلاقة بين اللغة والثقافة وكيف تساهم في تشكيل الهويات الفردية والجماعية.

تمحورت العديد من الأبحاث حول قضايا مثل تأثير العولمة على اللغات والثقافات المحلية، وكيفية المحافظة على التراث الثقافي واللغوي في مواجهة التغيرات المتسارعة. كما سلطت الأبحاث الضوء على دور الأدب في نقل التجارب الإنسانية والتعبير عن القضايا الاجتماعية والسياسية، ما أضاف أبعادًا جديدة لفهمنا للأدب كوسيلة للتغيير الاجتماعي والثقافي. في هذا السياق، عُرضت دراسات معمقة حول الترجمة ودورها في بناء جسور بين الثقافات المختلفة، حيث كانت الترجمة موضوعًا محوريًا في العديد من الأبحاث التي ناقشت التحديات التي تواجه المترجمين في نقل النصوص بما يحافظ على أصالتها وسياقها الثقافي. وقد أضافت هذه الأبحاث أبعادًا جديدة للفهم العالمي للأدب واللغة كوسائل لتبادل الأفكار والتجارب بين الشعوب.

من الجدير بالذكر أن المؤتمر تناول أيضًا التحولات التي تشهدها اللغات والأدب في العصر الرقمي، حيث تم تسليط الضوء على تأثير التكنولوجيا الحديثة على كيفية إنتاج النصوص الأدبية وتلقيها. وقدمت أبحاث حول كيفية توظيف الأدوات الرقمية في تحليل النصوص الأدبية، مما أتاح فرصًا جديدة للتفاعل مع الأدب بطرق مبتكرة ومختلفة.

هذا الكتاب يضم بين صفحاته نتائج عمل أكاديمي متميز يُظهر مدى التنوع والغنى الفكري الذي تمتعت به فعاليات هذا المؤتمر. فالأوراق البحثية المنشورة هنا ليست مجرد عرض لقضايا أدبية أو لغوية، بل هي محاولات جادة لاستكشاف العلاقات العميقة بين النصوص، الثقافات، والمجتمعات، وكيف يمكن أن يسهم فهم هذه العلاقات في تعزيز التواصل بين الشعوب في زمن يشهد فيه العالم تحديات متزايدة تتعلق بالتنوع الثقافي واللغوي.

نأمل أن يجد القارئ في هذا الكتاب إضافة غنية للنقاشات العلمية حول اللغات والآداب والدراسات الثقافية، وأن يكون محفزًا لمزيد من البحوث التي تسعى لفهم أعمق لتلك التخصصات الإنسانية التي تعد جزءًا أساسيًا من تشكيل هوياتنا وفهمنا للعالم. وختامًا، نود أن نعبر عن شكرنا لكل الباحثين الذين أسهموا بأبحاثهم في هذا المؤتمر، وكذلك لجميع الجهات المنظمة والداعمة التي ساهمت في إنجاح هذا الحدث الأكاديمي المتميز.

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Colonial Legacies and Identity in Lorraine Adams' 'Harbor': A Postcolonial Critique

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Abstract

An analysis of Lorraine Adams' "Harbor" (2004) from a post-colonial perspective looks at how the novel examines the effects of colonialism on Arab Algerian immigrants living in Boston. The study explores Algeria's history of French colonial domination, emphasizing the ways in which this past shapes the protagonists' identities and motivations. As the immigrants negotiate their Algerian history and the need to assimilate into American society, themes of identity crisis and cultural hybridity surface. Reflecting colonial power relations, the story tackles the social and economic marginalization they experience. The characters show resiliency in the face of these difficulties and create encouraging groups, signifying resistance to post-colonial marginalization. In addition to criticizing the persistence of colonial exploitation in contemporary globalization and American imperialism, "Harbor" highlights the ongoing injustices shaped by colonial histories. By means of individual narratives, the study highlights the enduring legacies of colonialism on contemporary socio-political realities with the aim of exploring the American perceptions of the Arab specially after the Ninth September as reflected in the story.

Keywords: Colonialism, Postcolonialism, Algerian immigrants, Identity

Introduction

The novel "Harbor" by Lorraine Adams explores the American immigrant experience, concentrating on the lives of Algerian stowaways in Boston. Although the book's main story is around the political and personal problems of these immigrants, it also touches on more general colonial themes, particularly in relation to the backgrounds of the individuals and the sociopolitical dynamics they experience. This research emphasized on the issue of Western representation of the Arabs with the assist of stereotype representation that utilized in Adams' Harbor (2004). From 1830 until 1962, Algeria was a French colony. Algerian society was deeply scarred by French colonization, which resulted in political instability, cultural disintegration, and economic dependency. The post-colonial circumstances in Algeria can be directly attributed to Aziz and his friends' migration. They are forced to leave their home country in search of better lives due to a lack of opportunities and ongoing conflict, demonstrating how colonial histories still have an impact on modern migration patterns.

The narrative begins with the protagonist, Aziz, fleeing Algeria due to the civil war while serving as a soldier in the Algerian army. After spending fifty-two days in the tanker hold, he finally arrives in the late 1990s. Aziz dives into Boston Harbor while covered in rags and bleeding. He swims ashore to start a new life in Boston, working as a dishwasher, deli worker, house painter, gas station attendant, and so on. Among his new acquaintances are his roommate Rafik, who covers his apartment in posters of Madonnas, deals in stolen items, has an American girlfriend named Heather, and introduces Aziz to Boston nightlife, which they

enjoy while wearing shoplifted suits. Among the others in his squad is Ghazi, a skilled architect who reads the Koran and watches Al Pacino movies to dull his depressive symptoms while doing the dishes. Mourad, Aziz's brother, gets a green card, lands a decent job, and starts living the American dream. Although they are surrounded by people who are not decent men and who deal in drugs, smuggling, credit card theft, and fraud, they are good men in general, and their lives also cross paths with those of the jihadists. An elderly Yemeni guy named Tahir Hussain helped Aziz in New York. He hires him to work in his shop. Aziz encounters other Arab Islamists and a dangerous terrorist named Antar. The Quran commands them to slay the infidels, as Antar, Dhaker, and other Arabs who gather in New York disclose. They attempted to admit Aziz but rejected the idea and returned back to Boston. The FBI arrests a group of Arab involved in terrorist acts Despite not being terrorists, Aziz, Mourad, and Ghazi are detained; nevertheless, all three are freed, with the exception of Ghazi, who was sentenced to "thirty-seven years" (Adam 2004: 292) for his involvement in other unlawful acts. But Mourad and his girlfriend flee to Mexico, and Aziz is sent to an unidentified location after being deported. The story comes to a conclusion here, but it's unclear what lies next for Aziz and the other young Arabs.

Literature Review

Studies on the issues of identity and displacement in post-colonial literature have been conducted in great detail by academics like Homi Bhabha and Edward Said. In "The Location of Culture" (1994), Bhabha developed the idea of cultural hybridity, which has had a significant impact on our knowledge of how people manage different cultural identities in post-colonial settings. Said's writings, especially "Culture and Imperialism" (1993), highlight how difficult it is for people to create their identities in the wake of colonialism.

The depiction of colonialism and colonial violence in "The Harbor" resonates with wider debates in postcolonial studies. Scholars such as Frantz Fanon ("Wretched of the Earth", 1961) and Achille Mbembe ("Necropolitik", 2003) have analyzed the lasting effects of colonial violence on societies and individuals, emphasizing how the traumas of the past continue to shape the present. . reality.

According to Amr Abdu Karim Sa'dawi (2002:9), the world is divided into good and evil, or black and white, by the Western worldview, particularly the American one. As a result, the West, or Americans in particular, perceive the Other as wicked. In the 19th and 20th centuries, American perceptions of Arabs were exoticized. This is due to the fact that their portrayal of Arabs is based on the Arabian Nights, wherein a Caliph still rules over the Arabs. One of the American writers a novelist, Mark Twain's *The Innocents Abroad* (1869) which carried out some exotic and negative images about the Arabs. Twain also uses stereotypes and disparaging language to characterize Arabs. One noteworthy line is:

"The Arabs are very dark-skinned, and some of them are very nearly black. Their features are not at all comely. They are not good-looking. The fellahs, or laborers, and the herdsmen of the plains are usually dressed in a short coarse shirt that falls a little below the knee, and is bound around the waist with a broad leather belt, from which hangs a long knife or a rusty horse-pistol. Their heads are bare, and their hair unkempt. They are long, gaunt, and unsightly" (Twain, 1869, p. 101).

This description is rife with derogatory overtones, emphasizing Arabs' physical characteristics in a way that highlights how ugly and backward they are thought to be. Words like

"unkempt," "not at all comely," "dark-skinned," and "unsightly" are especially indicative of Twain's prejudice.

Discussion and Analysis

The issue of identity, in particular the ways in which colonial histories affect people's identities individually and collectively. Aziz's conflict over his identity is a major theme in "Harbor." His voyage from Algeria to the US is representative of a larger post-colonial story about migration and the yearning for a place to call home:

"Aziz felt as if he were suspended between two worlds, neither fully Algerian anymore nor fully American. His memories of home were tainted by the violence that had driven him away, and yet, in America, he was forever an outsider, marked by his accent, his appearance, his very being." (Adams, 2004, p. 112)

As Homi Bhabha discusses, is the notion that individuals who have been colonized form a hybrid or mixed identity. Characters such as Aziz in "Harbor" demonstrate cultural hybridity by fusing aspects of their Algerian background with their new American environment:

"In the cramped apartment, the scents of cumin and coriander mingled with the sharp tang of American cleaning products, a blend that seemed to encapsulate Aziz's life: part old world, part new." (Adams, 2004, p. 76)

Aziz is shown in the beginning of the novel running away from his past and trying to start over in America. This reflects the focus of post-colonial theory on the diaspora and the ongoing migration of people to the West in pursuit of better opportunities from previously colonized areas (Ashcroft, Griffiths, and Tiffin, 1989).

The post-colonial theme of continuous conflict and instability in former colonies is reflected in the novel's depiction of the violence in Algeria that forced Aziz to emigrate. Long after formal colonization has ended, people are still affected by this brutality, which is a direct legacy of colonial control. "He had fled a country still reeling from its colonial past, where old hatreds had been rekindled and new ones had taken root, leaving no place safe." (Adams, 2004, p. 33). In addition, colonized peoples, presented as inferior and essentially different. In "Harbor," Aziz goes through this othering in the US, where people frequently treat him suspiciously because of his origin and race, particularly in the wake of 9/11:

"In the eyes of his neighbors, Aziz was an enigma, perhaps even a threat. They saw his dark skin, heard his accented English, and drew their own conclusions, shaped by fear and ignorance." (Adams, 2004, p. 198)

Adams shows in "Harbor" how preconceived notions about Arabs and Muslims are perpetuated in American society and politics, especially in the wake of the 9/11 attacks. Character Aziz Arkoun falls prey to these kinds of prejudices. Because of his race and faith, he is usually seen as a possible threat or terrorist. This impression is based on widespread misconceptions and anxieties about Arabs and Muslims rather than his actual deeds. This is consistent with what Edward Said (1978) writes about in "Orientalism," which is the West's creation of a stereotyped East in order to defend its hegemony and control.

Gender stereotypes are also addressed in "Harbor," with a focus on those that negatively impact Muslim women. Due to their gender and religious attire, female characters in the novel—like Aziz's sister—face additional layers of discrimination. They frequently reflect

Western stereotypes about Muslim women, which are that they are oppressed, subservient, and in need of liberation (Ahmed, 1992).

Aziz and other characters show agency and resistance in the face of adversity as they work to start over. This is consistent with post-colonial notions of agency and identity reclamation as well as resistance against prevailing narratives:

"Aziz refused to be defined by his circumstances. He took on menial jobs, learned English from old television shows, and dreamed of a day when he might call this new land home." (Adams, 2004, p. 145)

Adams portrays their struggle for dignity and self-determination, mirroring the broader post-colonial quest for agency and empowerment. The colonists' sense of superiority over the colonized is reflected in this marginalization, which is a reflection of colonial notions of inferiority and superiority.

The feeling of cultural displacement and the emergence of diasporic communities is another important theme in "Harbor." Together with other Algerian immigrants, Aziz creates a miniature version of their native country in the American cities. In the face of cultural alienation in their new surroundings, this diasporic community offers a tenuous sense of cultural continuity and belonging. It also draws attention to the two-edged nature of diaspora, where keeping cultural ties can occasionally impede complete integration into the host society. The conflict in these communities, where longing for one's native country coexists with the harsh realities of life as an immigrant, is explored in the novel. This dual existence highlights how diasporic identity is complex, as it is not entirely assimilated into the host country nor fully rooted in the homeland.

In addition to isolating him, this stereotype has an adverse effect on his mental health, making him feel disempowered and alienated. These incidents demonstrate how negatively these damaging stereotypes affect Arab and Muslim communities in the real world.

Conclusion

"Harbor," by Lorraine Adams, captures the complex dynamics of immigration, identity, and displacement while providing a nuanced exploration of post-colonial themes. The novel emphasizes the lingering effects of colonialism, the intricacies of hybrid identities, the dynamics of power and resistance, and the role that language plays in forming post-colonial subjectivities through Aziz's journey. Adams' treatment of these subjects offers a compelling story for post-colonial analysis and insightful information about the complex realities of immigrant life in a globalized society. A potent reminder of the lingering effects of colonialism and the difficulties post-colonial subjects face in negotiating their identities and realities can be found in Adams' "Harbor." Aziz's experiences serve as the lens through which the novel explores these themes, providing a profound commentary on the complexities of post-colonial.

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